

Visual catalog of profilometry scans used in: Warts and All: Evolutionary and ecological patterns in frog skin texture

BYU / YPM collection

This catalog presents thumbnail images associated with the profilometry scans used in this study. It is shared as a compact visual overview of the scan collection. Each image is accompanied by the specific museum code and body region. DA= dorsum anterior, DP= dorsum posterior, VA= venter anterior, VP= venter posterior. See supplemental Table 1 for species identity and metadata.

The images are shared as is. They have not been cropped, form-corrected, reconstructed, or processed in any way, and cannot be used to obtain surface metrics.

The raw profilometry scan files (either the complete set or species-specific) can be requested from the corresponding author. Refer to the original publication for specific details.

BYU46583_DA_

BYU46583_DP_

BYU46583_VA_

BYU46583_VP_

BYU46587_DA_

BYU46587_DP_

BYU46587_VA_

BYU46587_VP_

BYU46588_DA_

BYU46588_DP_

BYU46588_VA_

BYU46588_VP_

BYU46590_DA_

BYU46590_DP_

BYU46590_VA_

BYU46590_VP_

BYU46604_DA_

BYU46604_DP_

BYU46604_VA_

BYU46604_VP_

BYU46605_DA_

BYU46605_DP_

BYU46605_VA_

BYU46605_VP_

BYU46607_DA_

BYU46607_DP_

BYU46607_VA_

BYU46607_VP_

BYU51987_DA_

BYU51987_DP_

BYU51987_VA_

BYU51987_VP_

BYU51989_DA_

BYU51989_DP_

BYU51989_VA_

BYU51989_VP_

BYU51991_DA_

BYU51991_DP_

BYU51991_VA_

BYU51991_VP_

BYU52661_DA_

BYU52661_DP_

BYU52661_VA_

BYU52661_VP_

BYU52663_DA_

BYU52663_DP_

BYU52663_VA_

BYU52663_VP_

BYU52664_DA_

BYU52664_DP_

BYU52664_VA_

BYU52664_VP_

YALE1353_DA

YALE1353_DP

YALE1353_VP_

YALE12117_VA

YALE12117_VP_

YALE13294_DP

YPM0519_DA

YPM0519_DP

YPM0519_VA

YPM0519_VP

YPM0524_DA

YPM524_VA

YPM524_VP

YPM667_VP

YPM1259_VA_

YPM1259.VP_

YPM1261_DP

YPM1699_DA

YPM1699_DP

YPM1699_VA

YPM1699_VP

YPM3427_VP

YPM4815_DA

YPM4815_DP_

YPM4815_VP

YPM4816_DP

YPM4876_DA

YPM4878._VP

YPM5145_VA

YPM5195_DA

YPM5244_VA

YPM5275_DA

YPM6235_DA

YPM6235_VA

YPM6235_VP

YPM7080_DA_

YPM7080_DA

YPM7226_DA

YPM7226_DP

YPM7229_DP_

YPM7517_DA_

YPM7517_VP_

YPM7530_DA

YPM7530_DP

YPM7530_VA

YPM7530_VP

YPM7559_DA

YPM7559_DP

YPM7559_VA

YPM7559_VP

YPM8050_DA_

YPM8050_DP

YPM8050_VA

YPM8050_VP

YPM11990_VP_

YPM12212_DP

YPM12212_VA

YPM12212_VP_

YPM13008_DA

YPM13008_DP

YPM13008_VA

YPM13008_VP

YPM13396_DP

YPM13455_VP

YPM13737_VA_

YPM13738_VA

YPM20211_DA

YPM20211_DP

YPM20211_VP

YPM50121_DA_